

Beta₂-agonists for exercise-induced bronchoconstriction: data extraction inconsistencies and errors in the Cochrane review by Bonini et al. (2013)

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In 2013, Bonini et al. published a Cochrane review “Beta₂-agonists for exercise-induced asthma”:

Bonini M, Di Mambro C, Calderon MA, Compalati E, Schünemann H, Durham S, Canonica GW. Beta₂-agonists for exercise-induced asthma.

Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2013 Oct 2;(10):CD003564.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24089311>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd003564.pub3>

This document describes a number of data extraction inconsistencies and errors in Bonini’s (2013) review. Pages 11-15 were published previously in the supplementary file of an earlier paper:

Hemilä H, Friedrich JO. Many continuous variables should be analyzed using the relative scale: a case study of β₂-agonists for preventing exercise-induced bronchoconstriction.

Syst Rev. 2019 Nov 19;8(1):282.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc6865024>

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-019-1183-5>

The Supplement:

<https://ndownloader.figstatic.com/files/18955214>

https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6865024/bin/13643_2019_1183_MOESM1_ESM.pdf

Illustrations of six major extraction errors by Bonini are shown on pages 5-10.

The Cochrane Airways group was informed of the errors on 11 June 2020:

“The review by Bonini et al. has several errors related to data extraction, some of which are particularly large. For example, in the Bronsky (1995) and the Del Col (1993) trials, published FEV1 declines in the beta2-agonist tests appear 10 and 20 percentage points higher than in the original studies. There are also several cases of inconsistent data extraction...”

<https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD003564.pub3/read-comments>

However, the errors remain uncorrected in April 2024.

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Errors in other Cochrane reviews

Cochrane reviews are often promoted as high-quality systematic reviews that can be trusted: **“Cochrane: Trusted evidence. Informed decisions. Better health.”**
<https://www.cochrane.org/> (Accessed 2024-4-10).

However, the Cochrane review by Bonini et al. (2013) is not the only review that has been shown to be flawed.

In 2009, I found that there were several errors in the Cochrane review “*vitamin C supplementation for asthma*” (2009) [1]. For example, there were errors in data extraction; one trial had 20 participants, but only 11 participants were included in the Cochrane analysis. There were errors in the calculations, and the unpaired t-test was used when the paired test should have been used. My feedback was published in the (2010) version of the “2009” review [2,3].

The managing editor, Emma Welsh, wrote a response to my criticism in the (2012) version of the “2009” Cochrane review [4]. Simultaneously, the three analysis figures, which were the main focus of my critique, were removed from the review. In their absence, however, my feedback though originally valid became irrelevant. Furthermore, the remaining figures were renumbered so that the figure numbers in my feedback indicated real but different figures; therefore, readers would consider that I was confused. Finally, many responses by Welsh did not seem valid [5]. I contacted David Tovey, Editor-in-Chief of Cochrane, but our correspondence did not lead to any constructive efforts to correct the problem. After a year, I contacted COPE which stated that the original (2009) version [1] must be made available to readers; see a brief summary of the long process [6].

As a result of this process, one single PubMed record (#19160185) links to two different versions of the same “2009” Cochrane review. The PubMedCentral version (2009) includes all the original figures, but not my feedback [1]. The Cochrane Library version (2012) includes my feedback, but does not include the three analysis figures to which my feedback focused [4]. Finally, a third version of the “*vitamin C supplementation for asthma*” (2010) has both the original figures and my feedback, and is available at the University of Helsinki Digital Archive and Zenodo [2]. Furthermore, the errors that I pointed out in 2009 existed already in the 2001 version of the Cochrane review, so the review had been misleading readers over a decade [5]. Eventually, the review was withdrawn by Cochrane [7].

In 2011, I found that there were severe errors in the Cochrane review “*Zinc for the common cold*” (2011). I provided formal feedback in which I encouraged the authors to correct the flaws [8]. However, when the next version was published in 2013, almost all the errors remained. There was also plagiarism of text and data from another report [9]. Thus, the Cochrane editors had not checked that the flaws demonstrated in 2011 were corrected. Eventually, this process ended with the withdrawal of the zinc review [10], and with the retraction of the associated JAMA Clinical Evidence Synopsis [11-13].

In 2021, I found flaws in the Cochrane review on *vitamin C and pneumonia* (2020) [14]. For example, the authors stated “We included studies involving: 1. healthy adults and children receiving vitamin C supplementation for the prevention of pneumonia.” However, two trials (Coulehan et al. and Bancalari et al.) were included in the review despite the fact that they were common cold trials and neither mentioned pneumonia even as a secondary outcome. Furthermore, according to the Cochrane review, the number of pneumonia “events” in the Bancalari trial was 21 in each group. However, that was not the number of infections, but the number of children who had ≥ 1 infections. There were 46 infection events in the placebo group (N=30) and 38 in the vitamin C group (N=32). However, none of these 84 respiratory infections was pneumonia; they were the common cold [14].

The three Cochrane reviews described above and the Bonini et al. review are not to be trusted and do not help the reader to draw informed decisions based on evidence. Several authors have pointed out broader concerns with the Cochrane [15-20].

References

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References to the selected examples of errors in extraction by Bonini et al. (2013)

The following pages 5 to 10 illustrate the most severe extraction errors in the Cochrane review by Bonini et al. (2013).

A longer list of misleading or erroneously extracted data is shown on pages 11-15. The list was previously published in a supplement for Hemilä and Friedrich (2019) *Syst Rev.* 2019;8(1):282.

The references to the six selected examples of errors are given here:

Bronsky EA, Spector SL, Pearlman DS, Justus SE, Bishop AL.

Albuterol aerosol versus albuterol Rotacaps in exercise-induced bronchospasm in children. *J Asthma.* 1995;32(3):207-14.

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Prolonged effect of inhaled salmeterol against exercise-induced bronchospasm.

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<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7952623>

Shapiro GS, Yegen U, Xiang J, Kottakis J, Della Cioppa G.

A randomized, double-blind, single-dose, crossover clinical trial of the onset and duration of protection from exercise-induced bronchoconstriction by formoterol and albuterol.

Clin Ther. 2002 Dec;24(12):2077-87.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0149-2918\(02\)80098-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0149-2918(02)80098-4)

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12581546>

The selected examples from the Cochrane review by Bonini et al. (2013)

Bronsky et al. (1995) reported that FEV₁ decline was 6% in two salbutamol group (data above).

Bonini et al. (2013) added 10.0 and 20.0 pp to these figures (data below).

Table 1. Mean (SD) Change in Minimum FEV₁ from Pre- to Postexercise

	MEAN FEV ₁ (L)		
	PLACEBO	ALBUTEROL POWDER	ALBUTEROL AEROSOL
Preexercise (postdose)	1.54 (0.40)	1.70 (0.40)	1.69 (0.41)
Postexercise	1.21 (0.46)	1.59 (0.45)	1.58 (0.40)
Difference	0.35 (0.31)	0.11* (0.24)	0.11* (0.19)
Percent change	23 (20.0)	6* (13.0)	6* (11.0)

Bronsky (1995):

Bonini:

Appendix 3. Raw data for the maximal percent fall in FEV₁ calculations

Study ID	Beta-agonist arm			Placebo arm			Correlation
	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	
Anderson 2001 Salb Disk	13.42	13.23	27	39.4	17.58	27	0.46
Anderson 2001 Salb MDI	8.51	13.75	27	39.4	17.58	27	0.46
Blake 1999 Salb 180	3.8	7.5	25	13.5	2.7	24	
Blake 1999 Salm 25	7.99	10.2	26	14.0	11.5	23	
Blake 1999 Salm 50	7.34	10.3	26	14.0	11.5	23	
Boner 1994 Form 12	2.2	4.3	15	13.5	13.4	15	
Bronski 1995 Salb MDI	16.0	11.0	44	23.0	20.0	44	
Bronski 1995 Salb Pwd	26.0	13.0	44	23.0	20.0	44	

Del Col et al. (1993) published FEV₁ decline 0.76% and 2.37% in two salbutamol groups (data above).

Bonini et al. (2013) added 20 pp and 10 pp to the originally published figures.

ASSESSMENT OF JET SPACE DEVICE

TABLE 3. MAXIMUM PERCENT FALL IN FEV₁ POSTEXERCISE CHALLENGE TEST

<i>Treatment group</i>	<i>Maximum % fall of FEV₁</i>
Albuterol + Jet	0.76 ± 2.1 ^a
Albuterol + MDI	2.37 ± 5.1
Placebo + Jet	29.14 ± 15.1
Placebo + MDI	26.06 ± 16.1

^aMean ± standard deviation.

Placebo

DeBenedictis 1996 Salm 25	19.0	12.0	12	35.0	16.0	12	0.28
DeBenedictis 1996 Salm 50	15.0	13.0	12	35.0	16.0	12	0.33
DeBenedictis 1998 Salb	3.7	4.4	12	25.7	18.9	12	
Del Col 1993 Salb Jet	20.76	2.1	15	29.14	15.1	15	
Del Col 1993 Salb MDI	12.37	5.1	15	26.6	16.1	15	

Kemp et al. (1994) reported that on every time point salmeterol was more effective than salbutamol, indicated by smaller FEV₁ decline in the salmeterol test (5 vs. 7%, 8 vs. 25%, 13 vs. 27%) (above).

Bonini et al. (2013) selected salbutamol FEV₁ decline from time point 0.5 hours, but salmeterol FEV₁ decline from time point 11.5 hours. Thereby Bonini makes it falsely appear that salbutamol is more effective than salmeterol.

TABLE 2
MEAN FEV₁ (L) BEFORE AND AFTER EXERCISE AND MEAN MAXIMAL PERCENTAGE DECREASE IN FEV₁ AFTER EXERCISE FOLLOWING TREATMENT WITH PLACEBO, SALMETEROL, OR ALBUTEROL

Time After Dose	Placebo			Salmeterol			Albuterol		
	N	Mean	Decrease %	N	Mean	Decrease %	N	Mean	Decrease %
0.5h									
Before exercise	52	3.7		55	3.8		54	3.7	
After exercise	52	2.6	27	54	3.5	5	54	3.5	7*
5.5 h									
Before exercise	49	3.7		53	3.8		52	3.7	
After exercise	49	2.7	27	53	3.5	8†	52	2.7	25
11.5 h									
Before exercise	51	3.6		53	3.8		50	3.5	
After exercise	50	2.7	26	53	3.3	13†	50	2.6	27

* p < 0.001 for comparison with the placebo group.

† p < 0.001 for comparison with the albuterol group.

	Placebo	Salmeterol	Albuterol
Kemp 1994 Salb	7.0	5	27.0
Kemp 1994 Salm 42	13.0	8	27.0

Shapiro et al. (2002) reported four time points and on every time point formoterol was more effective than salbutamol, indicated by smaller FEV₁ decline in the formoterol test (above).

Bonini et al. (2013) selected salbutamol FEV₁ decline from time point 15 min, but formoterol FEV₁ decline from time point 12 hours. Thereby Bonini makes it falsely appear that salbutamol is more effective than formoterol.

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Table II. Mean (SD)* percentage decrease in forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV₁) from values before exercise challenge test.

Time After Dosing	Formoterol 12 µg (n = 19)	Formoterol 24 µg (n = 17)	Albuterol 180 µg (n = 19)	Placebo (n = 17)
15 min	4.0 (8.8)	6.0 (12.1)	10.0 (18.6)	31.1 (18.7)
4 h	9.0 (12.4)	9.9 (14.5)	27.5 (17.9)	32.7 (16.8)
8 h	11.2 (11.5)	13.3 (17.7)	32.3 (14.1)	32.9 (16.8)
12 h	12.4 (14.6)	17.5 (17.5)	35.3 (16.7)	32.4 (17.6)

*Means of the maximum observed percentage decrease in FEV₁ from 4 repetitions of each treatment per patient.

Shapiro 2007 Form 12	12.4	14.6	19	32.9	16.8	17
Shapiro 2002 Form 24	17.5	17.5	17	32.9	16.8	17
Shapiro 2002 Salb 180	10.0	18.6	19	31.1	18.7	17

de Benedictis et al. (1996) reported FEV₁ decline for 1 and 12 hours (above).

Bonini et al. (2013) select salmeterol FEV₁ data from time point 12 hours, but placebo FEV₁ data from time point 1 hour.

Table 2. – Maximum percentage decrease in FEV₁ at screening and after the first and the second exercise test with each treatment

Pt. No.	Screening	Maximum decrease in FEV ₁ %					
		Placebo		S _{LM} 25		S _{LM} 50	
		1 h	2 h	1 h	12 h	1 h	12 h
1	28	35	26	24	25	6	15
2	60	48	46	27	30	10	39
3	28	30	8	0	6	0	2
4	20	35	29	1	3	0	4
5	28	19	23	2	8	5	7
6	57	61	50	1	12	3	14
7	31	19	25	4	6	4	5
8	41	60	50	24	34	6	41
9	27	27	23	3	33	3	21
10	69	54	48	6	22	3	11
11	23	20	18	18	27	8	10
12	23	28	25	7	26	0	10
Mean	36	35	31	10	19	4	15
±SD	16	16	14	10	12	4	13

Pt: patients. For definitions see legend to table 1.

	Screening	1 h	2 h	1 h	12 h	1 h	12 h
DeBenedictis 1996 Salm 25	19.0	12.0	12	35.0	16.0	12	0.28
DeBenedictis 1996 Salm 50	15.0	13.0	12	35.0	16.0	12	0.33
DeBenedictis 1998 Salb	3.7	4.4	12	25.7	18.9	12	
Del Col 1993 Salb Jet	20.76	2.1	15	29.14	15.1	15	
Del Col 1993 Salb MDI	12.37	5.1	15	26.6	16.1	15	

Data extraction inconsistencies and errors in Bonini et al. (2013)

Our study did not intend to reproduce Bonini's main meta-analysis which was labeled Analysis 1.1 in their paper [11]. There are some errors and inaccuracies in the data extraction by Bonini and therefore exact reproduction of their Analysis 1.1 is not possible or relevant. Table S4 below describes the differences between Bonini's data extraction and ours.

Some of the errors are particularly large. In the Bronsky (1995) and the Del Col (1993) trials, Bonini added 10 and 20 percentage points to the published FEV₁ declines in the β_2 -agonist tests, see below.

In particular, given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, for included studies that reported on exercise tests at various times after the administration of the β_2 -agonist, we chose the shortest reported time after β_2 -agonist administration. Of the 44 studies we included in our analysis, 39 (87%) published data of exercise test that was carried out within 1 hour after drug administration, and the others were carried out within 3 hours, except Carlsen (1995) which reported only the 10-12 hour exercise test.

As an example of misleading data extraction by Bonini [11], Kemp (1994) compared salbutamol and salmeterol in three exercise tests that were carried out 0.5, 5.5, and 11.5 hours after the administration of the β_2 -agonist. In each time point, the FEV₁ decline was smaller after salmeterol than after salbutamol: 5% vs. 7% declines in the 0.5 hour test, 8% vs. 25% in the 5.5 hour test, and 13% vs. 27% in the 11.5 hour test, respectively. This means that at each time point salmeterol had a greater effect than salbutamol. However, in their Appendix 3, Bonini extracted the salbutamol FEV₁ decline from the 0.5 hour test (i.e. 7% FEV₁ decline) but the salmeterol FEV₁ decline from the 11.5 hour test (i.e. 13% FEV₁ decline) and thereby gives a biased impression that salbutamol was better than salmeterol because a smaller FEV₁ decline occurred after salbutamol. Such different time points were selected also for many other β_2 -agonist comparisons, see below. Such arbitrary selection of exercise test times biases the presentation and analysis in the Bonini review.

The percentage decline in FEV₁ values in Table S3 indicate the change that occurred in the exercise test. The changes are negative, but the minus sign is not included.

For the references to the studies and to a description of the studies, see Bonini [11]:

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD003564.pub3>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24089311>

Table S4: Data extraction inconsistencies and errors in Bonini et al. (2013)

Study	Original report Source in the report	Bonini et al. [10] stated Appendix 3: Raw data for the maximal percent fall in FEV ₁ calculations
Blake (1999)	FEV ₁ decline: 5.36% (Salmeterol 25) [1 hr test] 5.64% (Salmeterol 50) [1 hr test] 13.5% (Placebo) [1 hr test] Table 3: 1 hour exercise test	FEV ₁ decline: 7.99% (Salm 25) [6 hr test] 7.34% (Salm 50) [6 hr test] 14.0% (Placebo) [12 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 1 hour exercise tests. Furthermore, Bonini used different exercise test data for placebo and salmeterol. Furthermore, for salbutamol (Albuterol) and its placebo, Bonini gives the 1 hour exercise test results (3.8% and 13.5%, respectively). The same exercise test time should be used in the comparisons of the placebo and the β_2 -agonists.
Bronsky (1995)	FEV ₁ decline: 6% (Albuterol Aerosol) 6% (Albuterol Powder) Table 1	FEV ₁ decline: 16.0% (Salb MDI) 26.0% (Salb Pwd) 10% and 20% have been added in error by Bonini to the published results.
Bronsky (1999)	FEV ₁ decline: 1.4% (Salmeterol Diskus) [1 hr] 0% (Salmeterol Diskhaler) [1 hr] 10.5% (Placebo) [1 hr] Fig 1 and text p. 503: 1 hr exercise test	FEV ₁ decline: 5.6% (Salm Disk) [12 hr test] 5.7% (Salm Diskhal) [6 hr test] 12.1% (Placebo) [12 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 1 hour exercise tests.
Bronsky (2002)	FEV ₁ decline: ~6% (Formoterol 12 μ g) [15 min] ~6% (Formoterol 24 μ g) [15 min] Fig 1: 15 min after dosing	FEV ₁ decline: 17.0% (Form 12 μ g) [12 hr test] 14.6% (Form 24 μ g) [12 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 15 min tests.
Daugbjerg (1996)	FEV ₁ decline: 9% (Formoterol) [3 hr test] Page 685 bottom. 3 hour exercise test. This 9% is reported as “median” in the original report.	FEV ₁ decline: 11% (Form 12) [12 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases overtime, we used the 3 hour test.

Study	Original report Source in the report	Bonini et al. [10] stated Appendix 3: Raw data for the maximal percent fall in FEV₁ calculations
De Benedictis (1996)	FEV ₁ decline: 10% (Salmeterol 25) [1 hr test] 4% (Salmeterol 50) [1 hr test] Table 2: 1 hour exercise test	FEV ₁ decline: 19.0% (Salm 25) [12 hr test] 15.0% (Salm 50) [12 hr test] 35.0% (Placebo) [1 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 1 hour tests. The 1 hour test indicates substantially greater efficacy of salmeterol since the FEV ₁ declines are much smaller. Furthermore, Bonini used different exercise test data for placebo and salmeterol. The same exercise test time should be used in the comparison of placebo and β_2 -agonist.
Del Col (1993)	FEV ₁ decline: 0.76% (Albuterol + Jet) 2.37% (Albuterol + MDI) Table 3	FEV ₁ decline: 20.76% (Salb Jet) 12.37% (Salb MDI) 20% and 10% have been added in error by Bonini to the published results.
Green (1992)	FEV ₁ decline: 2.7% (Salmeterol) [1 hr test] Table 1: 1 hour exercise test.	FEV ₁ decline: 3.2% (Salm 50) [9 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 1 hour exercise test, though the difference is not great in this case. Furthermore, the exact FEV ₁ decline in the 9 hr test reported by Green (1992) was 3.4% and not the 3.2% stated by Bonini.
Grönneröd (2000)	FEV ₁ decline: 5.40% (Formoterol 4.5 μ g) [15 min] 2.50% (Formoterol 9 μ g) [15 min] 18.4% (Placebo) [15 min test] Table 2: 15 min exercise test	FEV ₁ decline: 9.2% (Form 4.5) [12 hr test] 5.4% (Form 9) [12 hr test] 18.4% (Placebo) [15 min test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 15 min tests. For placebo, Bonini gives the FEV ₁ decline in the 15 min exercise test, but for formoterol results, Bonini seems to give the FEV ₁ decline in the 12 hour exercise tests (9.29% and 5.43%) rounded down.
Kemp (1994)	FEV ₁ decline:	FEV ₁ decline:

Study	Original report Source in the report	Bonini et al. [10] stated Appendix 3: Raw data for the maximal percent fall in FEV₁ calculations
	5% (Salmeterol) [0.5 hr test] 7% (Albuterol) [0.5 hr test] 27% (Placebo) [0.5 hr test] Table 2: 0.5 hour exercise test We did not include the Kemp study in our analysis, since it was not a cross-over study.	13.0% (Salm) [11.5 hr test] 7.0% (Salb) [0.5 hr test] 27.0% (Placebo) [0.5 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 0.5 hr tests. For the parallel test on salbutamol (Albuterol), Bonini gives the FEV ₁ decline in the 0.5 hour exercise test, but the salmeterol FEV ₁ decline is from the 11.5 hour exercise test. In the 0.5 hour test of salmeterol, the FEV ₁ decline is 5%, which is smaller than the decline in the 0.5 hour test of salbutamol (i.e. 7%), see left-hand side. Bonini's selection of the 0.5 hour exercise test for salbutamol and the 11.5 hour test for salmeterol misleads readers since the FEV ₁ decline is greater on salmeterol treatment indicating that salmeterol is less effective. However, on each of the three reported time points, salmeterol was more effective in preventing FEV ₁ decline.
König (1981)	FEV ₁ decline for Study 1 is reported in Table 1 of König (1981)	Bonini does not include Study 1 results. Study 1 had 24 participants; of these 24 participants, 17 participated in study 2, for which Bonini gives the results. Study 1 had 10 min delay between inhaled metaproterenol and the exercise test. Study 2 had 1 hr delay between inhaled metaproterenol and the exercise test. Bonini writes as if there was a single trial which used two exercise tests "Time of exercise challenge after drug administration: 10 min, 1 hour" whereas König carried out two separate studies which used 10 min and 1 hour delay before the exercise tests.
McAlpine (1990)	FEV ₁ decline: 14.1% (Salbutamol) [2 hr test] Table 1: 2 hour exercise test	For the other studies, Bonini gives the results for all published β_2 -agonists. For the McAlpine (1990) study, Bonini gives the formoterol results, but not the salbutamol results published in the same table.
Newnham (1993)	FEV ₁ decline: ~1% (Salmeterol) [1 hr test] 27.1% (Placebo) [1 hr test] Fig 1 and text p. 441	FEV ₁ decline: 12.8% (Salmeterol) [12 hr test] 32.0% (Placebo) [6 hr test] Given that the effect of β_2 -agonists decreases over time, we used the 1 hour tests. Furthermore, Bonini used different exercise test data for placebo and salmeterol.
Pearlman (2006)	FEV ₁ decline: 2.61% (Formoterol 12 μ g) [15 min]	FEV ₁ decline: 7.6% (Form 12) [12 hr test]

Study	Original report Source in the report	Bonini et al. [10] stated Appendix 3: Raw data for the maximal percent fall in FEV₁ calculations
	1.02% (Formoterol 24 µg) [15 min] 11.11% (Placebo) [15 min test] Table 3: 15 min exercise test	5.9% (Form 24) [12 hr test] 13.2% (Placebo) [4 hr test] Given that the effect of β ₂ -agonists decreases over time, we used the 15 min tests. Furthermore, Bonini used different exercise test data for placebo and formoterol. The same exercise test time should be used in the comparison of the placebo and the β ₂ -agonists.
Philip (2007)	FEV ₁ decline: 10.2% (Salmeterol) [2 hr test] Table 2: 2 hour exercise test	FEV ₁ decline: 10.7% (Salm 50) [8.5 hr test] 21.8% (Placebo) [2 hr test] Given that the effect of β ₂ -agonists decreases in time, we used the 2 hour tests. Furthermore, Bonini used different exercise test data for placebo and salmeterol.
Richter (2002)	FEV ₁ decline: 6.3% (Terbutaline) [30 min test] 22.4% (Placebo) [30 min test] Table 3: 30 min exercise test	FEV ₁ decline: 8.50% (Terb 500) [60 min test] 25.1% (Placebo) [60 min test] For the parallel tests on formoterol and salmeterol, Bonini gives the FEV ₁ declined in the 30 min exercise tests (5.7% and 7.6%, respectively), but for the terbutaline and placebo FEV ₁ declines they give the results from the 60 min exercise test. The same time exercise test should be used in the comparison of placebo and β ₂ -agonist.
Shapiro GS (2002)	FEV ₁ decline: 4.0% (Formoterol 12 µg) [15 min] 6.0% (Formoterol 24 µg) [15 min] Table II: 15 min exercise test	FEV ₁ decline: 12.4% (Form 12) [12 hr test] 17.5% (Form 24) [12 hr test] 10.0% (Salb 180) [15 min test] Given that the effect of β ₂ -agonists decreases over time, we used the 15 min tests. For salbutamol, Bonini gives the FEV ₁ decline in the 15 min exercise test. Thereby the comparison with formoterol (i.e. 12 hr test) is biased and gives an impression that salbutamol is better, though formoterol is better in both the 15 min and the 12 hr tests when compared with salbutamol at the same time points. The same time exercise test should be used in the comparison of placebo and β ₂ -agonists. Finally, Bonini's reference is erroneous, to a paper by a different Shapiro GG (1990): https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/2145791 and not to the Shapiro GS (2002) though Bonini's data are from the 2002 paper: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12581546